

How to assess the state of consciousness in head-only electrically stunned rabbits

Introduction

Head-only electrical stunning is intended to induce unconsciousness in rabbits, lasting until death occurs through bleeding.

It is required to monitor that rabbits are immediately rendered unconscious after stunning and remain unconscious until death. If any animal-based indicator (**ABI**) of consciousness are observed, rabbits must be promptly re-stunned using appropriate backup methods to prevent unnecessary pain, distress, and suffering.

This factsheet contains:

1. The method for the assessment of the state of consciousness after head-only electrical stunning in rabbits.
2. The most relevant (i.e. valid, feasible and repeatable) ABIs to be used in the assessment.
3. Procedures for calculating appropriate sample size for the assessment.

Methods for the assessment

Place for the assessment: at two different stages (Fig. 1)

- **Stage 1:** Immediately after stunning and before bleeding to assess the effectiveness of the stun.
- **Stage 2:** During bleeding to assess that unconscious rabbits do not recover consciousness before death.

Figure 1. Places for the assessment. The red segments are the observation area.

Sampling procedure and recommended ABIs:

Stage 1:

- Observe individual rabbits for minimum 3-4s (if possible).
- Effective induction to unconsciousness is indicated by the presence of tonic-clonic seizure (see description of the outcome of unconsciousness in **Table 1** and video accessible via QR code)
- Then, assess the three other ABIs of the state of consciousness, outlined in **Table 1** and demonstrated in the videos accessible via QR codes in **Figure 2** and record the outcome of the ABIs for each rabbit.

Stage 2:

- Position yourself at a distance from the neck-cutting area where ABIs of consciousness may appear in rabbits (e.g., approx. 8s after carotid sectioning).
- Observe each rabbit individually for 8-12 s.
- Assess the ABIs of the state of consciousness (as detailed in **Table 1** and demonstrated in the videos accessible via QR codes in **Figure 2**) and record the outcome of the ABIs for each rabbit.

Figure 2. Indicators of consciousness. Blue arrows highlight the areas of the rabbit's body to focus on, with videos accessible via the linked QR codes.

Table 1. Animal-based indicators (ABIs) assessed and description of the outcomes of unconsciousness and consciousness in rabbits subjected to head-only electrical stunning in the two stages.

Stage	ABIs	Outcome of unconsciousness	Outcome of consciousness
1	Tonic-clonic seizure	Rabbit shows arched and stiff neck (<i>i.e.</i> necks appear parallel to the ground) and paws and ears held tightly close to the body. Then followed (or not) by kicking action and/or leg paddling that can be either rhythmic or erratic	General loss of muscle tone and a completely relaxed and flaccid body, with no neck tension.
1&2	Breathing	Absence of opening of the mouth and thoracic or abdominal movements associated to cessation of inhalation and expiration. Presence of one movement is not considered as breathing.	Presence of rhythmic breathing considered as a minimum of two openings of the mouth and thoracic or abdominal muscles associated to inhalation and expiration with similar cadence.
1&2	Spontaneous blinking	Rabbit does not open/close eyelid on its own (fast or slow) without stimulation.	Rabbit opens/closes eyelid on its own (fast or slow) without stimulation.
1&2	Vocalisations	Absence of single or repeated short and loud shrieking (screaming).	Single or repeated shrieking (screaming).

Sample size calculation

Case 1. You want to assess the prevalence of rabbits in a batch with at least one outcome of consciousness. By determining *a priori* the expected prevalence and the relative precision you want to achieve, you can calculate the sample size.

Information needed:

1. Population size: total number of rabbits in the flock
2. Expected prevalence
3. Relative precision: the accuracy you want to achieve
4. Confidence level: usually used at 95%

Example: you want to assess, in a batch of 5000 rabbits, an expected prevalence of 1% with 30% relative precision (it means that the result will be something like $1 \pm 0.3\%$) and 95% confidence level.

According to the following table, you need to assess approx 4226 animals.

Precision, %	Expected prevalence, %									
	1	2	3	4	5	10	15	20	25	
10	38032	18824	12422	9220	7300	3458	2177	1537	1153	
20	9508	4706	3106	2305	1825	865	545	385	289	
30	4226	2092	1381	1025	812	385	242	171	129	
40	2377	1177	777	577	457	217	137	97	73	
50	1522	753	497	369	292	139	88	62	47	

Case 2. You want to detect if the prevalence in the batch is above or below a certain 'level'.

Information needed:

1. Population size: total number of rabbits in the batch
2. Prevalence threshold I want to detect
3. Confidence interval: usually used at 95%

Example: the number of rabbits in the batch is approx. 5000 and you want to be able to determine if the prevalence in the batch is over 1% or not.

According to the following table, you need to assess 290 animals. If you detect no animals with outcome of consciousness among the 290 animals, it means that the prevalence in the batch is below 1%.

Threshold, %	Total number of rabbits in the batch					
	200	500	1 000	5 000	10 000	20 000
0.5	190	349	450	564	581	589
1	155	225	258	290	294	296
2	105	129	138	147	148	148
3	78	90	94	98	98	99
4	62	69	71	73	74	74
5	51	56	57	59	59	59

Online calculation tool for both Case 1 and 2 is provided [here](#).

For more detailed information, please access the webinar on "Welfare Assessment During Electrical Stunning in Rabbits" and/or the slides by scanning the QR codes on the right

Webinar

Presentation

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